

DIGISPAC

Project TED2021-131237B-C21

DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN

DOCUMENT INFORMATION

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COORDINATED PROJECT INFORMATION	
Acronym	DIGISPAC
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Project Title	Evaluation of the digital twin paradigm applied to precision irrigation and fertigation (DigiSPAC)
Coordinator	Jaume Casadesús, ORCID 0000-0001-7036-8212
Principal Researcher	Jaume Casadesús
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Project Abstract	<p>The concept of the Digital Twin (DT) is rapidly emerging in various application areas where process optimization is sought through the complementarity of real-time monitoring and simulation. The DIGISPAC project has evaluated and promoted the applicability of this paradigm to the monitoring and management of irrigation in processing tomatoes, vineyards, and almond orchards. DIGISPAC's framework for applying DT to irrigation and fertigation emphasizes the combination of different monitoring technologies typical of precision agriculture (water meters and sensors in soil and/or plants with IoT connectivity, satellite remote sensing, meteorological records, and online forecasts) with real-time simulations of soil water dynamics and crop development. This ultimately feeds into the automated generation of personalized annual strategies and daily irrigation and fertigation prescriptions, which are transmitted machine-to-machine to irrigation controllers. A fundamental aspect of the DT concept is the interaction between simulations and observations. By comparing simulations with reality, DT models can be more site-specific. Methods have been established to incorporate the main types of parameters monitored by sensors and remote sensing into the models. Field trials in processing tomatoes, vineyards, and almond orchards have demonstrated the feasibility of precision irrigation control using DT. In the case of woody crops, the feasibility of managing irrigation by connecting stem microtensiometers to DTs has been tested, which required enhancing the fault tolerance of these sensors and complementing them with simulations. The ability of DTs to combine monitoring with simulation has also been applied to the analysis of water production functions in various crops, such as processing tomatoes and almonds. Furthermore, these capabilities proved very useful for analysing the impact of a drought event on a regional scale. This highlights the applicability of DTs on a large scale, generating interest from groups such as irrigation communities and fruit and vegetable producer cooperatives. The DIGISPAC project has helped establish the integration logic between observations, simulations, and site-specific customization for the precise and autonomous management of irrigation and fertigation for various crops. The project has also contributed to the technological maturity of the IRRIDESK platform, reaching the first fully commercial users of DT applied to irrigation, projected for 2026, at both the farm and large-scale levels.</p>
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Subproject Title, PID, Responsible and affiliation	Subproject 1 Subproject 2	TED2021-131237B-C21: Jaume Casadesús Brugués (IRTA) TED2021-131237B-C22: Carlos Mario Campillo Torres (CICYTEX)
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Executive Summary

The Data Management Plan (DMP) for the TED2021-131237B-C21 project describes the data generated, analyzed, and disseminated during the implementation of the so-called DIGISPAC research project. This project is coordinated with 2 subprojects:

1. DIGISPAC Subproject 1. Code TED2021-131237B-C21. Recipient: Institut de Recerca i Tecnologia Agroalimentàries (IRTA)
2. DIGISPAC Subproject 2. Code TED2021-131237B-C22. Recipient: CICYTEX (Extremadura)

This DMP covers the entire data lifecycle, from data generation and collection to processing, analysis, storage, security, long-term preservation, and publication in the Subproject 1 only. The DMP complies with data protection standards, as well as intellectual property and exploitation requirements, following the general principle "as open as possible, as closed as necessary" established at the EU level (EC, 2017; SE, 2019).

This DMP uses existing standards appropriate to each discipline, while establishing mechanisms to encourage data sharing and open access by institutions, individuals, and other stakeholders involved in scientific research. This approach utilizes different standards in terms of formats, context, and content.

This project is part of a coordinated project with the objective of "Validate the potentiality of a system of digital twins representing the Soil-Plant-Atmosphere Continuum (SPAC) of each irrigation management zone, as a frame for decision-making and knowledge discovery in Precision Irrigation".

Accordingly, development of the project followed these specific objectives:

1. To define a system of SPAC digital twins addressed to support the requirements of Precision Irrigation.
2. To develop and validate the appropriate procedures to obtain a reliable and accurate representation of the state of soil and crop in real irrigated plots, through assimilation of local sensors and Earth observation data in the digital twins.
3. Evaluate the suitability of the digital twin approach for analyzing the water productivity functions of processing tomato and almond, in different growing scenarios in Spain.
4. To evaluate the feasibility of precision irrigation control in field trials based on estimates of Stem Water Potential by the digital twin. This would demonstrate the potentiality of using data enriched by the digital twin in the rationale of decision making. These data will not come from their direct measurement in the real world, but from simulations. This would facilitate devising better cost-effective sensor deployments and more intuitive and accurate rules for decision making.
5. Evaluate the feasibility of dynamic fertigation control in field trials based on crop growth forecasted by the digital twin. Besides the direct interest in fertigation management, this will demonstrate the potentiality of extending the digital twins to support inter-related functionalities such as the combined management of water and fertilizers.

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1. DATA DESCRIPTION

1.A.1. Relationship of data with the Project

DIGISPAC focuses on defining a Digital Twin (DT) system of the Soil-Plant-Atmosphere SPAC system aimed to support automation and management tools for Precision Irrigation

The DIGISPAC Subproject 1 Data Management Plan (DMP) shows how data has been handled, stored, protected and shared during the development of the project. The DMP also provides an overview of the nature and accessibility of data, as well as its management in terms of long-term storage and security.

This DMP covers the Subproject one, aimed at **defining a Digital Twin (DT) of the Soil-Plant-Atmosphere Continuum (SPAC) system to be used in digital tools for supervision, management and automation of Precision Irrigation.** Subproject1 developed and validated the appropriate procedures to obtain a reliable, accurate and daily-updated representation of the soil and crop conditions during the irrigation seasons. It also evaluated the feasibility of the remote sensing and modelling technologies within a DT approach, to analyze water productivity functions for almonds. This subproject evaluated automated irrigation scheduling based on DTs, at commercial scale, in vineyards and almond orchards. It also tested the feasibility of precision irrigation control by DTs fed by stem water potential measurements and estimates. Finally, the application range of irrigation tools based on DTs was upscaled from individual farms to collectives including hundreds of farms, such as irrigation districts and farmer's cooperatives.

1.A.2. Format of data

The data are provided in open and freely readable formats:

- .csv (experimental data and data dictionaries)
- .xlsx (supplementary analysis sheets)
- .txt (README files)
- .pdf (technical and scientific documentation)
- .docx (manuscripts and drafts)
- .json (configuration of the Digital Twins)
- .geojson (vector data of the experimental plots)
- .tiff (raster data from remote sensing)

UTF-8 encoding is used, with tabular structures accompanied by variable dictionaries.

1.A.3. Data reuse

The datasets can be reused for:

- Studies on Digital Twin applications to agricultural water management
- Studies on digital support tools for irrigation scheduling
- Studies related with automated irrigation scheduling in vineyards and almond orchards
- Studies on supervision of agricultural drought episodes at real time
- Studies upscaling water management from individual farms to farm collectives and regions

1.A.4. Data origin

All the data are original of the combination of DIGISPAC and related projects by the research team and were generated within the experimental framework of these projects, at the facilities of each project partner. These related projects include IRRINTEGRAL (RTI2018-099949-R-C21) and ET4DROUGHT (PID2021-127345OR-C31). No pre-existing datasets have been reused besides those projects.

1.A.5. Estimated size

The expected size of the data is large, depending on the datasets. Datasets of excel, csv., pdf. are of the order of gigabytes (>10 GB), with individual data files <10 MB, distributed as follows:

- Data downloaded from the DT platform
- Miscellaneous measurements in field
- Documentation and metadata
- Analysis and publication files

Storage is managed through the computing facilities of each partner, with periodic backups and plans for deposition in open repositories (Zenodo & CORA). Copies of the DT databases will be maintained on the internal facilities of IRTA. They will be made available to any user upon request.

The data generated and collected are represented in the following table:

Table 1. Data Collected and Generated in the Subproject 1 of DIGISPAC.

Dataset Name	Category	Format	Data Origin	Data Utility
Dataset from field trials on almond	Experimental data	.txt, .csv, .xls, .geojson, .json, .zip	Field trials on almond (Agramunt, Lleida) from project DIGISPAC	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Digital Twin applications to agricultural water management •Digital support tools for irrigation scheduling •Studies on automated irrigation scheduling in almond
Dataset from field trials on vineyard	Experimental data	.txt, .csv, .xls, .geojson, .json, .zip	Field trials on vineyard (Raimat, Lleida) from project DIGISPAC	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Digital Twin applications to agricultural water management •Digital support tools for irrigation scheduling •Studies on automated irrigation scheduling in vineyards

Scientific publications	Scientific publications	.pdf	Scientific peer scientific publications where DIGISPAC project has contributed	Scientific community: plant-water relations, remote sensing. Also irrigation district managers, waterbody agencies and agritech companies
Presentations in Workshops and conferences	Presentations	.pdf	Slides used in oral presentations in workshops and conferences	Dissemination of Digital Twin application to irrigation at three scales: farm, community and region

See Annex 1 for more information related to the access, (re)use conditions and related research outputs.

2. FAIR Data

2.A. Findable Data (including metadata)

2.A.1. Mechanisms for locating, searching and identifying data

Part of the experimental data obtained during the DIGISPAC project has been published in scientific articles and made available in the ZENODO (DIGISPAC community). **Zenodo** is an open-access, multidisciplinary data repository developed and operated by **CERN** within the framework of the **OpenAIRE** initiative. It provides a reliable platform for the publication and preservation of research outputs, including datasets, software, publications, and other digital materials, in accordance with the **FAIR** (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) principles and the guidelines of the **European Open Science Cloud (EOSC)**. Since we are also dealing with geospatial data (even in situ data will be mostly georeferenced) JSON/GeoJSON format will be used for the metadata. This would enhance human readability as compared to other metadata formats such as XML. In addition, GeoJSON is the standard format for defining collections, assets and items in SpatioTemporal Asset Catalogs (STAC).

Zenodo assigns **Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs)** to all published records, ensuring their persistent and unique identification, and allowing them to be easily discovered through common internet search engines and scholarly databases. The repository supports rich metadata descriptions compliant with international standards such as **DataCite**, **Dublin Core**, and **Schema.org**, facilitating interoperability and citation.

Through its integration with OpenAIRE and CERN's robust infrastructure, Zenodo guarantees long-term data preservation, open access, and global visibility for research outputs across all scientific disciplines.

2.A.2. Structure and nomenclature of data files

The consortium will give a clear and hierarchical structure to the generated datasets. Files will be uniquely identifiable and versioned. The file nomenclature has been defined as follows:

- Project Acronym name
- Institution acronym
- Main Topic: main subject in relation to the content of the data

- Year: date range
- Data provided, for instance: watermeters, soilWaterContent, irrigationPrescriptions ...
- Format extension, for example: .xlsx

See some examples:

- DIGISPAC_IRTA_VINEYARD_2024_PLOT1_watermeters.xlsx
- DIGISPAC_IRTA_VINEYARD_2024_irrigationPrescriptions.xlsx
- DIGISPAC_IRTA_droughtCicle_ALMOND_2024_neutronProbe.xlsx

In addition, the following conventions will be observed:

- Be consistent with character casing. Recommend the use of uppercase or capitalize the first letter each word, except for the file extension which is recommended in lower case.
- Low bar "_" will be used in file names to delimitate units of metadata;
- "-" can be used for words that need to be globbed together, or put all words together capitalizing the first letter of each word: e.g. DATA-MANAGEMENT-PLAN, or DataManagementPlan.
- no punctuation, no accents, (e.g. ;, :, á, ñ,)
- no special characters (e.g. \$, @, %, #, &, *, (,), !);
- a new file with the same name as an existing file will automatically replace the existing file;
- for raw data "raw" will be added at the end of a filename and the file is made read-only;
- For data exceeding a size limit, or for an ensemble of data files, those will be shared in DIGITAL.CSIC within a .ZIP compressed folder¹. This folder will follow the naming convention detailed above, the "extension" corresponding to the compressed folder extension used (standard .zip). Caution will be made to avoid name repetition, for a clear identification of data. A supporting README.md text file will also be provided, indicating clearly the content of each individual file.

2.A.3. Use of keywords for data localization

Project data deposited in public repositories provide searchable keywords in the metadata files themselves. In the case of institutional and multidisciplinary repositories, the reference vocabulary is the [AGROVOC Multilingual Thesaurus](#).

For exclusive specialty terms not found in standard controlled vocabularies, expressions that match common search criteria in scientific publications specific to those disciplines are used. It recommends the use of at least 5 significant keywords for each dataset.

2.A.4. Version Control

In the case of openly published data (i.e., files deposited in CORA.RDR) use DOI version control by default. DOI version control allows a dataset to be updated after publication and to cite a specific version or all versions.

Regarding restricted-access data files, the TEAMS platform, and its associated applications, SHAREPOINT and ONEDRIVE, all from Microsoft, allow the recovery of previous versions. Therefore, the TEAMS platform always maintains a single version—the most recent one—without the need to resort to file naming (to identify versions) or registering these versions with the recorded changes in databases. Any significant change affecting the content of the data is documented in "README.txt" files.

¹ OSF allows for large files and subfolders.

2.B. Accessible Data

2.B.1. *Data available in open and restricted data*

By default, all data associated with scientific publications have been deposited in open access repositories, unless there is a specific reason not to do so. For cases such as those indicated below, the data will not be publicly disseminated:

- Data obtained with the permission of third parties, but without their consent to make public dissemination of them.
- Data that cannot reveal the identity of persons.
- Data that compromises the protection of the intellectual or industrial property of a partner or partners, or of the institution itself (IRTA).
- Data pre-processed or pending analysis, unless there is a clear reason to do so.
- Other sets of data that, for legal and/or contractual reasons, cannot be shared.

The data will be made public once the scientific publication has been published.

2.B.2. *Data Access*

During the project, qualitative (focus groups) and quantitative data are obtained from experimental studies (laboratory and pilot plant) and surveys with consumers.

Data is recorded mainly on paper or entered directly into a computer using EXCEL (Microsoft 365), which includes the data matrices.

Photos, videos, and other recording information are taken with a camera or mobile phone and gradually uploaded to the research group's Teams.

For data that may be openly accessible, widely accepted international standard formats will be used, in accordance with the following data types:

- Graphics and photographs: jpeg, tiff
- Tables and databases: csv
- Text: docx, pdf

Data published in the form of datasets will be hosted in ZENODO repository, but also linked to the CORA.RDR repository (Catalan Open Research Area – Research Data Repository) for open access dissemination.

All team members have access to the data stored in the TEAMS group. However, only published data are accessible through data repositories, with only data pending publication remaining open to restricted access.

Data is deposited in repositories simultaneously with—or prior to—submitting the manuscript to scientific journals for consideration.

Initially, and specifically for scientific publications undergoing peer review, temporary access will be granted to the reviewers of the work to consult the data subject to publication. At the same time, an embargo period will be established for access by the public. This embargo will expire when the work is formally accepted for publication.

These data will be retained and publicly accessible for at least 10 years.

2.B.3. Methods or programs necessary for data access

As discussed in section 2.B.2, on data typology, for open access data, standard and open formats are used (csv, .txt, .tiff, .jpg, .pdf) and no specific programs are needed to open and access the data.

If the use of specific programs or methods is necessary to manage certain data, this contingency is adequately commented on in the metadata file (README.TXT).

2.B.4. Use Restrictions

Generally, data deposited in open access repositories are published under the Creative Commons CC BY 4.0 license. Therefore, there are no general restrictions on the use of published data. However, certain files can be embargoed until related results are published in journal articles.

The data owner (not necessarily the project's IP), but also anyone responsible for managing the data they produce, determines which license will be used when DIGISPAC data is published in both ZENODO and CORA.RDR. The project's recommendation, as stated above, is to choose CC BY. Therefore, individuals or institutions that use openly deposited data must acknowledge the DIGISPAC project and the source of the data in any resulting publication.

All data generated by participants has been anonymised either by the market research company contracted (in most cases) or by IRTA researchers in the case of focus groups. In some cases, video and audio recordings were made during the studies. Since this information allows responses to be linked to a specific individual, it is considered confidential and will not be shared. Transcripts of the audio files will be included without identifying the participants.

2.B.5. Data Access conditions

Within the project, all resources are accessible to all members of the research team and to certain individuals within the project team folder. The list of personnel with access to the data is established by the principal investigator (PI) through the role assignment provided by the TEAMS platform and in accordance with the needs of the project.

Restricted access conditions will only be established in cases of data pending exploitation (commercial or scientific), sensitive data, third-party data for which the PI does not hold intellectual property rights or open licenses for its use, or other interests that could be considered legitimate. See Annex 1 for a list of open and restricted data.

The data is shared among the members of the corresponding subproject, and the PIs of the subproject will authorize the participation of personnel who are not part of the research team when deemed appropriate. The existence of a committee to manage access to project data is not considered necessary, regardless of the type of access (open or restricted). During the execution of this project, all resources are accessible to all members of the research team and to certain individuals on the work team (doctoral students).

2.C. Interoperability Data

2.C.1. Data Interoperability

Throughout the development of the databases and their associated metadata, various commonly used international standards have been used. Depending on the nature of the data, the most common standards used in the project databases are listed below:

- Date: ISO 8601:2004 standard for date formats (YYYYMMDD; year-month-day).
- Units of measurement: International System of Measurements.
- Counts: Natural numbers.
- Percentages: Based on counts (cases that meet a certain condition in relation to the total number of cases). Examples: incidence, impact, or abundance.
- Species names: scientific names (use of standard vocabularies e.g., AGROVOC, NCBI Taxonomy)

Therefore, we will use formats readable via frequently non-commercial software, or which are not specific to a certain software. The file formats to be used for storage of the generated data are listed in the table below.

Data Type	Preferred Formats ²	Editing Software
Generic data file	.dat	Text editors (as Notepad, Wordpad)
Documents	.txt .pdf .odt	Text editors (as Notepad, Wordpad) LibreOffice, MS Word Standard PDF viewers
Spreadsheet	.csv	Text editors, Spreadsheet software (as LibreOffice or MS Excel)
Geospatial raster	.tif	GIS software (as QGIS or ArcGIS)
Geospatial vector	.geojson .shp	GIS software (as QGIS or ArcGIS)
Raster figures	.png .jpg	Standard image viewers
Geospatial	.netcdf	GIS software (as QGIS or ArcGIS)
Vector figures	.eps .svg	Standard image viewers
Markup language	.md .tex	Text editors Online interpreters (as https://markdownlivepreview.com/) LaTeX editors/compiler
Archive file format	.zip .tar	Standard file archives (as WinZip, gunzip)

² I bold the suggested option

To ensure reproducibility and possible interoperability it is also crucial that every dataset is accompanied by a detailed documentation in form of the README.txt file. The rest of the non-standardizable variables are also described in the associated README.TXT files that contain the descriptors of the different data sets, their description, coding if applied and their preparation in cases of use of calculated variables.

2.C.2. Use of standard vocabularies

The DIGISPAC project does not create new ontologies or specific vocabularies. As a general rule, the project uses terms included in the AGROVOC standard vocabulary, a vocabulary coordinated by the FAO (Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations) that incorporates common terms in agricultural sciences or, vocabularies used by the repositories themselves, such as the NCBI taxonomy for species nomenclature or others considered relevant.

2.D. Reusable data

2.D.1. Licensing and Data Reuse

All data generated within the framework of the DIGISPAC project are sufficiently described to be understandable and reusable in their corresponding documentation files.

In principle all relevant research data generated by the project will be reusable by third parties unless special restrictions apply which will be indicated in the accompanying metadata. We think that our data can be of interest to by other scientists in the field of Agronomy, Plant physiology, Remote sensing and Climate Change studies. Future research should also concentrate on long-term studies of Water Use Efficiency. The data quality is ensured by different measures. These include validation/consistency of the samples, replication, and comparison with results of similar studies.

Regarding open data licenses, as mentioned above, the project recommends publishing data under the Creative Commons CCBY license.

2.D.2. Data Embargo Periods

For datasets linked to scientific publications, during the manuscript review period and subsequent editorial production, editors and reviewers have been provided with an exclusive, restricted link for data access.

Likewise, during the article review period, an embargo has been placed on access to the data by the public. The embargo expires when the article is formally accepted for publication by the journal. This allows access and reuse of all data associated with a given publication at that time.

2.D.3. Restrictions on data reuse

All experimental data linked to open-source publications, and properly deposited in repositories (e.g., CORA.RDR), are available without access or use restrictions once the embargo period established during the editorial review process of the work ends.

Access to datasets that may be subject to intellectual and industrial property rights has been closed due to confidentiality and exclusivity issues. In principle, these data are not expected to be made available in public repositories; instead, they are maintained on the institutional TEAMS platform, within the corresponding project folder.

2.D.4. Data Quality

Data quality control begins during data collection and is the primary responsibility of the project data creator/owner, who ensures that the recorded data reflects the actual facts, responses, and observations. Therefore, the data quality in this DMP is controlled and verified by the PIs of each task.

Regarding possible errors during data entry/digitization, methods for manual verification by at least two people have been established. Once the data integrity and consistency with the originally collected data have been verified, they are validated. Validation was carried out by the researcher responsible for the task to which the data are associated.

In the databases managed by the project, usually Excel files, a section for database document control has been included (if necessary). This document control includes the identification (person and date) of those involved in reading, verifying, and validating the data. This documentary practice constitutes an IRTA standard, established in its own technical instructions and linked to the ISO 9001 and ISO 17025 standards applied by IRTA—and, by extension, by its researchers—in the development of their research activities.

2.D.5. Data Reuse Period

Generally, the project establishes a 10-year preservation period. This is also the minimum period for reuse, with its extension to be assessed once the period ends. Each institution is responsible for the management and maintenance of its data and, therefore, its preservation and reuse beyond the established preservation period.

3. Resource Allocation

3.A. Cost estimation for FAIR Data

The solutions for storing and preserving project data discussed so far do not currently incur any costs.

In all cases, IRTA's Research Data Management Service, which specializes in research data management, knowledge management, intellectual property rights, and FAIR data, offers support to those responsible for the various activities in identifying how to properly generate and manage the data at no cost.

3.B. Specify how the cost is expected to be covered

Given the above, the final paragraph of section 6.A does not require allocating funds to cover data storage and preservation.

3.C. Data Management Responsibilities

The responsibility for collecting, quality controlling, and storing experimental data from the various project tasks falls on the researcher responsible for that task, as also proposed in the project application. This data is stored and accessible to all project members on each subproject's own intranet (TEAMS). Task leaders follow the specifications of this DMP in their practical application.

3.D. Data Long-Term Preservation

The data collected or produced during the project, as previously mentioned, are stored in the DIGISPAC space of the IRTA TEAMS platform. This space currently has no time limitations regarding data preservation.

The dataset will increase in value over the years because of its fundamental impact in the Agronomy, Biology and Climate Change fields, also in the future. Long-term studies and interdisciplinary research are desirable and intended.

Regarding data corresponding to scientific publications and having been deposited in open repositories (CORA.RDR), a minimum retention period of 10 years is expected. In the event of any changes in the data storage policies of these platforms, regarding costs, the strategy to be followed will be studied with the assistance of the IRTA Research Data Management Service.

4. Data Storage and Security

The data generated during the execution of the Subproject 1 DIGISPAC project will be stored in the "Project Unit," that is, in the Teams activity devices. These services share space (the data is stored in the Azure cloud). Cloud storage facilitates collaboration with the group; in the case of Teams, it allows internal messages to be integrated with documents/data. The stored data should be considered a single copy since it is stored in the same space (Azure cloud). However, because this location provides data redundancy, version history, and 93-day retention in the first and second level recycle bins, we can consider it as "two" copies.

Subproject 1. The storage and preservation of all data for Subproject 1 of the DIGISPAC project is organized within the TEAMS platform provided by IRTA institutionally. Within this platform, there is a dedicated space (DIGISPAC) accessible only to researchers and project team members, using personalized identification and access keys. All project information is organized into folders with names clearly descriptive of their content. Specifically, the information regarding the project's is organized in folders named by their corresponding task and a brief description (e.g., "Task 2.2.3. ANF removal"). Furthermore, IRTA servers follow a data security protocol that includes an automated workflow for daily backups. TEAMS uses the resources of the Microsoft cloud, which owns TEAMS, so the data retention, security, and recovery policies directly align with TEAMS policies and also respond to IRTA's needs in this area. The TEAMS platform and its maintenance costs are covered by IRTA's own resources, so no specific project expenses are expected to be allocated. Secondary storage of experimental data in other research data repositories (e.g., CORA.RDR) will be considered. However, this option is not recommended for sensitive or confidential data, which will remain under IRTA's control on the TEAMS platform. Data subject to IRTA's restriction policies, that is, those susceptible to protection due to intellectual or industrial property issues, will remain in IRTA's institutional services cloud (TEAMS platform).

DIGISPAC does not collect personal data. Hence, confidentiality and integrity of sensitive data are always maintained, respecting the privacy of individuals and complying with current regulations, The General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) of the European Union and the Organic Law on Data Protection and Guarantee of Digital Rights (LOPDGDD) in Spain.

5. Ethical aspects

The established measures covered the legal and ethical requirements complying with data protection laws (LOPDGDD and GDPR). In all cases, an informed consent was obtained for data collection, storage, and sharing, including for long-term preservation.

- **Data sharing and reuse:** sensitive data will only be shared in an encrypted manner, so that no one other than the person who retrieved them will be able to access the sensitive data.
- **Long-term preservation:** The anonymised data will be stored indefinitely for further scientific use.
- address how data will be archived and preserved for the long term, ensuring it remains accessible and usable for future research.

All participants in this project undertake to adhere to the fundamental principles of research integrity, such as reliability, honesty, respect and responsibility in relation to the data produced throughout the project.

6. Other support in the development of the DMP

This DMP has been developed based on the template of the Data Management Plan proposed by the CSUC, the consortium that brings together the Catalan universities, the Balearic Islands and Jaume I of Castelló province, to facilitate the adoption of programs and initiatives related to the Open Science movement. There is also an online CSUC tool (eiNa.DMP) that allows the preparation of the DMP online. This document also follows the FAIR good data management practices. of the European Commission (2016).

In the preparation of this DMP, the advice of IRTA's Research Data Management Service was also considered.

7. Responsibility and resources

7.1. Responsible of the Data Management Plan

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8. Resources of interest

1. AGROVOC Multilingual Thesaurus: <https://agrovoc.fao.org/browse/agrovoc/en/>
2. CORA.RDR. Url: <https://www.csuc.cat/es/servicios/cora-repositorio-de-datos-de-investigacion/>
3. ZENODO DIGISPAC community. Url: <https://zenodo.org/communities/digispac>

4. Dataverse. Url: <https://dataverse.csuc.cat>
5. DDI. Url: <https://ddialliance.org/>
6. DMP online. Url: <https://dmponline.dcc.ac.uk/>
7. Dublin Core. Url: <https://www.dublincore.org/>
8. EOSC Portal. Url: <https://eosc-portal.eu/>
9. eiNA DMP. Url: <https://dmp.csuc.cat/>
10. European Commission. 2016. Guidelines on FAIR Data Management in Horizon 2020. Url: http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/grants_manual/hi/oa_pilot/h2020-hi-oa-data-mgt_en.pdf
11. How to create a DMP (argos, OpenAIRE). Url: <https://argos.openaire.eu/splash/>
12. Metadata Standards Directory. Url: <http://rd-alliance.github.io/metadata-directory/>
13. NCBI Taxonomy. Url: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/taxonomy>
14. Registry of Research Data Repositories. Url: <http://www.re3data.org/>

9. Annex I. Summary of research data produced

TABLE 2. DATA PRODUCED THROUGHOUT THE DIGISPAC SUBPROJECT1 AND ITS ACCESS AND REUSE CONDITIONS

Task	Data	Status	PI	Access / Restrictions	Data Typology	Format	Repository	Size	Dissemination (data and articles)
	Dataset from field trials on almond	Published 30/12/2025	Jaume Casades ús & Ana Pelechá	Citation is required	Settings and inputs to Digital Twins	.txt, .csv, .xls, .geojson, .json, .zip	ZENODO	<10 MB	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18099927
	Dataset from field trials on vineyard	Published 30/12/2025	Jaume Casades ús & Ana Pelechá	Citation is required	Settings and inputs to Digital Twins	.txt, .csv, .xls, .geojson, .json, .zip	ZENODO	<10 MB	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18099928
	Evaluating the impact of drought and water restrictions on agricultural production in irrigated areas through crop water productivity functions and a remote sensing-based evapotranspiration model	Published	Joaquim Bellvert	Open-access	Publication	pdf	j.agwat	<25 MB	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agwat.2025.109319
	Almond yield prediction at orchard scale using satellitederived biophysical traits and crop evapotranspiration combined with machine learning	Published	M.Quint anilla-Albornoz & Joaquim Bellvert	Open-access	Publication	pdf	fagro	<25 MB	doi: 10.3389/fagro.2025.1667674

Task	Data	Status	PI	Access / Restrictions	Data Typology	Format	Repository	Size	Dissemination (data and articles)
	Assimilation of Sentinel-2 Biophysical Variables into a Digital Twin for the Automated Irrigation Scheduling of a Vineyard	Published	Joaquim Bellvert	Open-access	Publication	pdf	water	<25 MB	https://doi.org/10.3390/w15142506
	Soporte digital a la gestión del riego a tres niveles: parcela, comunidad de regantes y regional	Published	Jaume Casade sú	Open-access	Presentation	pdf	ZENODO	<10 MB	10.5281/zenodo.18100696
	Suport digital a la gestió de l'aigua en l'agricultura: des de nivell finca fins a col·lectiu i regional	Published	Jaume Casade sú	Open-access	Presentation	pdf	ZENODO	<10 MB	10.5281/zenodo.18100797

